

A Study on Socio Economic Status of Micro Women Entrepreneurs in Chennai City

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Rahamath Nisha, A.
“A Study on Socio Economic Status of Micro Women Entrepreneurs in Chennai City.” *Shanlax Internatioal Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 220–24.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586433>

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Abstract

A micro entrepreneur plays a vital role in the development of state as well as a nation. In this study the researcher considers the street vendors as micro entrepreneur. Street vendors are low income vulnerable group of people who engage themselves in trading activities with a meager investment. Both primary and secondary data was used for the study. The primary data was collected form 100 respondents based on simple random technique from Chennai city. Percentage analysis and Garrett ranking technique was used for analysis. It is concluded that the women entrepreneurs should be provided with financial assistance to improve their standard of living which leads to growth of economy to some extent.

Introduction

A street vendor is a person who offers goods or services for sale to the public without having a permanent built-up structure but with a temporary static structure or mobile stall (or head-load). Street vendors could be stationary and occupy space on the pavements or other public/private areas, or could be mobile, and move from place to place carrying their wares on push carts or in cycles or baskets on their heads, or could sell their wares in moving buses.

Review of Literature

Sandeep Kumar Baliyan and Vikas Deepak Srivastava (2016) conducted a study on Socio-Economic Condition of Street Vendors from the Gender Prospective, It is aimed to examine the socio-economic profile of street vendors from the gender perspective and to identify the different problems faced by the Female street vendor as compare to male counterpart. The researchers have collected primary data with the help the detailed schedule in Lucknow city, Uttar Pradesh from 400 street vendors engaged in different business activities. It is found that female street vendors faced the more problems rather than the male street vendors. They are livings in worst condition as compared to male. Since

Joseph Kweku Assan (2015), “India’s street vendors and the struggle to sustain their livelihoods and informal enterprises: Unionization, political action and sustainable development”. It is proposed that more attention should be given to labour in the informal

sector and that those in such occupations should be recognized and protected by national and state laws as workers with labour rights

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the socio economic profile of the micro women entrepreneur
- To examine the problems encountered by respondents. Collection of Data

Both primary and secondary data was collected for the study. The primary data was collected through a well structured questionnaire and the secondary data was collected from the books, journals and magazines.

Sampling Method

The researcher has selected 100 micro women entrepreneurs form Chennai city using convenient sampling method.

Tools Used For Analysis

For the analysis the statistical tool were used such as simple percentage and garrett ranking technique.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Below 30 years	18	18
	31-40 years	33	33
	41-50 years	27	27
	Above 50 years	22	22
Marital Status	Unmarried	28	28
	Married	36	36
	Widow	23	23
	Separated	13	13
Family Type	Nuclear Family	84	84
	Joint Family	16	16
Education Qualification	Uneducated	31	31
	Primary	25	25
	Secondary	16	16
	Higher Secondary	28	28
Nature of Vending	Fruits and Flowers	36	36
	Vegetables	16	16
	Cooked Food items	18	18
	Household Utensils	10	10
	Readymade Garments	20	20

Source: Primary data

Table 1 reveals the socio economic profile of the respondents. Among the respondents 33 per cent of them are in the age group of 31-40 years. 22 per cent of the women are in the age group of above 50 years.

Out of 100 respondents 36 per cent of the women are widows and separated. 28 per cent of the respondents are unmarried and the remaining 36 per cent of them are married.

84 per cent of the respondents are living in the nuclear family and 16 per cent of the respondents are living in the joint family.

Among the sample respondents 31 per cent of them are uneducated. 21 per cent of them have studied primary level. 28 per cent of them have studied the higher secondary level education.

The women entrepreneurs are engaged in numerous vending activities, 36 per cent of the respondents are vending fruits and flowers, 20 per cent of the respondents are vending the readymade garments, 18 per cent of the respondents are vending the cooked food items, 16 per cent of the respondents are vending the vegetables and the remaining 10 per cent of the respondents are vending the household utensils.

Table 2 Socio Economic Profile of the Respondents

Socio Economic Variables		Frequency		Percentage	
Total Earning Members	1	46		46	
	2	33		33	
	3	21		21	
Annual Family income	Below Rs.50000	51		51	
	Rs.50001-1,00,000	42		42	
	Above Rs.1,00,000	5		5	
Number of Working Hours	6 Hours	24		24	
	8 Hours	42		42	
	Above 12 Hours	34		34	
Financial Assistance	Money lenders	69		69	
	Banks	31		31	
Basic Amenities in Market place	Amenities	Yes	No	Yes	No
	Water	63	47	63	47
	Toilet	44	56	44	56

Source: Primary Data

A single member is earning in 46 per cent of the respondents family, two members are earning in 33 per cent of the respondents family and in 21 per cent of the respondents family 3 members are earning.

51 per cent of the respondents are earning an annual income of below Rs.50,000. 42 per cent of the respondents are earning an annual income between Rs.50,001- 1,00,000 and 5 per cent of the respondents are earning Above Rs.1,00,000.

42 per cent of the respondents are working up to 8 hours. 34 per cent of the respondents are working above 12 hours.

69 per cent of the respondents are availing financial support from the local money lenders. 31 per cent of the respondents are availing financial support from the banks since their earnings are low the banks hesitates to provide financial assistance for the micro entrepreneurs.

Basic amenities in the work place 63 per cent of the respondents are availing sufficient water facilities in the market place and the remaining 47 per cent of the respondents are not availing proper water facilities.

56 per cent of the respondents are not availing the toilet facilities because they are mobile vendors.

Table 3 Problems Faced by the Respondents

Problems	Frequencies							Total	Mean Score	Rank
Health Issues due to more working hours	31	20	17	6	8	10	8	8323	83.23	7
Harassment from the local authorities	18	12	16	20	18	6	10	8442	84.42	5
Uncertainty of employment	10	10	21	20	16	11	12	8524	85.24	3
No separate union for street vendor	15	16	19	13	13	14	10	8472	84.72	4
Restriction on Bank Loans	34	21	10	11	9	11	4	8673	86.73	1
Fluctuation of Sale	7	11	10	23	11	18	20	8284	82.84	6
Lack of market amenities	20	10	12	11	12	20	15	8567	85.67	2
Garrett Table Value	79	81	82	84	87	90	95			

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals the problems faced by the respondents. Restrictions on bank loan secure the first rank with the mean score of 86.73. The street vendors do not have a stable income every month so the micro entrepreneurs face difficulty in availing loan from the banks. Lack of market amenities has secured the second rank with the mean score of 85.67. Uncertainty of employment secures the third rank with the mean score of 85.24. The street vendor are informal self employers so there is no separate laws, it has secured the fourth rank with the mean score of 84.72. Harassment of local authorities has secured the fifth rank with the mean score of 84.42. Fluctuations of the sale have secured the sixth rank with the mean score of 82.84 and health issues have secured the seventh rank with the mean score of 83.23.

Findings

- Among the respondents 33 per cent of them are in the age group of 31-40 years.
- 36 per cent of the women are widows and separated. Single parental system has forced them to become a micro entrepreneur.
- 84 per cent of the respondents are living in the nuclear family
- 31 per cent of them are uneducated
- 36 per cent of the respondents are vending fruits and flowers
- A single member is earning in 46 per cent of the respondents family
- 51 per cent of the respondents are earning an annual income of below Rs.50,000
- 69 per cent of the respondents are availing financial support from the local money lenders
- 63 per cent of the respondents are availing sufficient water facilities in the market place
- 56 per cent of the respondents are not availing the toilet facilities because they are mobile vendors.

Suggestion

It is suggested that the earnings of micro entrepreneurs in very low in order to achieve a proper economic growth the banks can extend financial services to the street vendors through which they can enhance their standard of living. The local authorities can regulate a law for unorganized micro entrepreneurs.

Conclusion

To accomplish a better growth the state and central government can encourage the women entrepreneurs. Although it has provided various financial services to vulnerable group of people still they are untouched. The women entrepreneurs should be provided with financial assistance to improve their standard of living which leads to growth of economy to some extent.

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